

Studies on some ternary complexes of Cu^{II} with diamines and hydroxy acid

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Abstract : Solution studies on ternary complexes of Cu^{II} with diamines (A) viz. ethylenediamine, 1,2-diaminopropane, 1,3-diaminopropane, *o*-, *m*- or *p*-phenylenediamine and salicylic acid (H₂L) in the ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 have been investigated by pH metric technique at $\mu = 0.2 M$ (NaClO₄) and at temperature 30 ± 0.1 °C in aqueous media. The formation constant values for ternary system Cu^{II}-diamine-salicylic acid has been calculated and probable species like H₂L, HL, CuALH, CuAL₂ etc. are pruned with FORTRAN IV computer program. These values are discussed in terms of basicity of primary and secondary ligand, size of chelate ring, $\Delta \log K_T$ values and different statistical factors such as metal-ligand interaction, structure of ligands and intermolecular ligand-ligand interactions. Structure of complexes is suggested on the basis of molecular modeling.

Keywords : Ternary complexes, formation constants, molecular modeling.

The ever increasing importance of ternary complexes especially those involving ligands containing functional groups identical with those present in the enzymes viz. -COOH, -NH₂, -CONH etc. is obvious from the application of such complexes in many analytical and biological reactions¹⁻⁵. Diamines are widely studied in binary systems^{6,7} but so far literature does not support where diamines are used as primary ligand in ternary systems.

The present paper reports the determination of the formation constants of CuAL type of complexes where A = ethylenediamine or 1,2-diaminopropane or 1,3-diaminopropane or *o*-, *m*-, *p*-phenylenediamine and H₂L = salicylic acid.

Results and discussion

Diamines has protonable -NH₂ groups and using the method of Irving and Rossotti⁸, the pK_a values have been found and compared with literature values. Mode of coordination of diamines with Cu^{II} is a function of two -NH₂ groups and also pH⁹. In present study, it is found that complexation of diamines with Cu^{II} is with two -NH₂ groups. Salicylic acid acts as a secondary ligand as formation constant values of binary complexes it forms with Cu^{II} are less than that of diamines (selected) complexes. The formation of ternary complexes was confirmed by the shape of pH titration curves i.e. separation

of pH-metric titration curves representing the ternary systems in comparison to curve for the binary metal complex with secondary ligand.

The relative stabilities of the mixed ligand complexes compared to corresponding binary complexes and can be quantitatively expressed in terms of $\Delta \log K_T$ where

$$\Delta \log K_T = \log K_{CuA}^{CuA} - \log K_{CuL}^{CuL}$$

For square planar ternary complexes (+)ve or less (-)ve than -0.60 values of $\Delta \log K_T$ indicate their higher stabilities over corresponding binary complexes¹⁰.

The proton ligand formation constant values for various diamines are in the following order and are in accordance with the reported values^{11,12} : 1,3-diaminopropane > 1,2-diaminopropane > ethylenediamine > *p*-phenylenediamine > *m*-phenylenediamine > *o*-phenylenediamine.

The formation constants of ternary complexes are in the following order : *p*-phenylenediamine > *m*-phenylenediamine > *o*-phenylenediamine > ethylenediamine > 1,2-diaminopropane > 1,3-diaminopropane.

This order can be explained in terms of basicity of primary and secondary ligand, structure of ligand, size of chelate ring and steric hinderance. Formation constant values for ternary complexes with aromatic diamines are

higher than aliphatic diamines. Ternary complexes with aromatic diamines as primary ligand will have delocalization of the π -electrons in the metal chelate ring as in benzene ring¹³. Formation constant values for ternary complexes of aromatic diamines follow the same order as proton ligand formation constant values for the aromatic diamines as β_{HA} and β_{H_2A} values of *p*-phenylenediamine > *m*-phenylenediamine > *o*-phenylenediamine.

In comparison among ternary complexes involving aliphatic diamine as primary ligand, 1,3-diaminopropane ternary complexes are having lowest value for the formation constant although 1,3-diaminopropane has highest basicity, Moreover 1,3-diaminopropane forms six membered chelate ring and other aliphatic diamines form five membered chelate ring with Cu^{II} ¹⁴. Complexes with five membered chelate ring formation are considered to be more stable than six membered ring¹⁵. Ethylenediamine ternary complexes are higher in formation constant values than 1,2-diaminopropane although pK_1^H value of ethylenediamine is lower than 1,2-diaminopropane. Steric hinderance due to the presence of $-CH_3$ group of 1,2-diaminopropane near to one of the donor atoms may be probable cause for lowering the formation constant value of 1,2-diaminopropane ternary complexes¹⁵.

Species distribution curves : The ternary species of stoichiometry are AH, AH_2 , HL, H_2L , $CuAH$, CuA_2 , $CuLH$, CuL_2 , $CuAL$, $CuAL_2$, $CuAL(OH)$ and have been assumed in different chemical models. The species distribution diagrams for all the systems under investigation have been obtained for different metal to ligand A and L ratio solutions which supports formation and stability of $CuAL$ 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes. There is striking difference in the species distribution in ternary system in

1 : 2 : 2 solutions where CuA_2 and CuL_2 species become dominant because of preferred structural characteristics of binary species¹⁶. $CuAL(OH)$ species appear with increase in volume of alkali added. In order to demonstrate these quantitative trends the species distribution diagram obtained in 1 : 1 : 1 solution of Cu^{II} -*o*-phenylenediamine (A)-salicylic acid (H_2L) are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Species distribution diagrams for $CuAL$ in molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 1.

The possibility of hydroxo and polynuclear species is tested and some were detected by using FORTRAN IV computer program¹⁷.

A tentative structure has been proposed on the basis of previous studies and calculation of molecular mechanics. It is reported that diamines are bidentate ligands and $[Cu(diamine)(H_2O)]^{2+}$ can be isolated from acidic solution. Keeping on this analogy with above, it is proposed that Cu^{II} -diamine-salicylic acid is 4-coordinated complex with 2 sites occupied by diamines groups and two sites by bidentate salicylic acid groups ($-COOH$ and $-OH$

Table 1. Formation constant values of diamines and complexes of Cu^{II}

Temp. = 30 ± 0.1 °C, $\mu = 0.2 M dm^{-3}$ ($NaClO_4$)

	EDA	1,2-DAP	1,3-DAP	<i>o</i> -PDA	<i>m</i> -PDA	<i>p</i> -PDA
$\log \beta_{HA}$	9.85	10.04	10.90	4.61	5.01	6.22
$\log \beta_{H_2A}$	16.79	16.69	19.75	6.42	7.57	9.21
$\log \beta_{CuAH}$	10.55	10.50	9.98	9.55	9.56	9.87
$\log \beta_{CuA_2}$	19.60	19.60	17.17	14.32	13.79	15.76
$\log \beta_{CuAL}^{CuA}$	8.85	8.17	7.87	9.27	9.38	9.39
$\log \beta_{CuA_2LH_2}^{CuA}$	0.37	0.17	0.15	0.96	0.31	0.11
$\log \beta_{CuAL_2}^{CuA}$	1.2	2.16	1.56	0.37	1.02	1.03
$\log \beta_{CuAL(OH)}$	-3.6	-4.3	-3.5	-1.4	-3.2	-3.7
$\Delta \log \beta_T$	-0.68	-1.36	-1.66	-0.26	-0.15	-0.14

Standard deviation : 0.11-0.39, $\log \beta_{LH} = 12.38$, $\log \beta_{H_2L} = 14.96$, $\log \beta_{CuLH} = 9.35$, $\log \beta_{CuL_2} = 13.38$, where, A = diamine, H_2L = salicylic acid.

groups). Moreover molecular modeling for a representative complex Cu(diamine)(salicylic acid) was carried out by using a software Hyperchem¹⁸ to see probable structure with minimum strain energy. Calculations were carried out for both the possibilities i.e. where hydroxy acid behaves as monodentate or bidentate ligand. The strain energy was found to be 13–20 kcal/mol for all ternary complexes except for Cu^{II} (*m*-phenylenediamine)(salicylic acid) where it was 58.10 kcal/mol when salicylic acid was coordinated at two sites. It confirms that proposed possible structure for all the present complexes is 4-coordinated.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. All solutions were prepared in the conductivity water. Metal solution was prepared and standardized complexometrically¹⁹. Perchloric acid was standardized with standard NaOH solution and constant ionic strength was maintained with an inert electrolyte sodium perchlorate (NaClO₄) (Riedol). pH metric titrations were carried out with Systronics μpH meter 361 with capacity ±0.01. The titration solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The double walled glass cell is used in the nitrogen atmosphere to avoid any side reactions.

The following five sets were prepared for titrations : [1] acid (1 milimole), [2] acid (1 milimole) + primary ligand (0.1 milimole), [3] acid (1 milimole) + secondary ligand (0.1 milimole), [4] acid (1 milimole) + primary ligand (0.1 milimole) + metal perchlorate (0.1 milimole), [5] acid (1 milimole) + primary ligand (0.1 milimole) + secondary ligand (0.1 milimole) + metal perchlorate (0.1 milimole). Total volume used in the cell was 50 ml and ionic strength was maintained 0.2 M (NaClO₄) at temperature 30 ± 1 °C in all sets. Titrations were carried out with carbonate free standardized 0.2 M NaOH solution.

From the titration data formation constants were calculated by weighted least squares method of Sullivon *et al.*²⁰.

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